

A Roadmap to Effective Evaluation Plans

Quick Reference & Guidelines

The Evaluation Mindset

Before you start, put yourself in an “*evaluation mindset*” by asking *What, So What* and *Now What?*¹ Your responses will become the components of your Evaluation Plan.

1. WHAT?

Planning:

- Identify your program’s name, objectives, and SMART goals.
- List your key actors (e.g. partners, collaborators, communities of interest, etc.)
- Define the needs of your key actors by identifying their interests and the main points of interaction they have with your program and other actors.
- Establish a clear timeline and specific work plan.
- Outline a dissemination strategy for your findings. Ensure you are tailoring your message to different audiences.

2. SO WHAT?

Collection & Analysis:

- Develop your evaluation questions.
- Decide on your evaluation approaches and establish indicators.
- Collect data about your program.
- Develop and complete your data analysis plan.
- Compare your original objectives, goals, timelines, and milestones with your actual data.
- Reflect on the impact of your evaluation.

3. NOW WHAT?

Dissemination & Decision-Making:

- Ensure evaluation findings are presented in a clear, achievable, and actionable manner.
- Determine how the findings from your evaluation will be shared and used for programmatic & strategic decision-making.
- Apply your dissemination strategy by tailoring your evaluation results to different audiences.
- Report your Findings.

¹ Patton, M. Q. (2008). Utilization-focused evaluation. SAGE Publications.

Evaluation Plan Sections & Questions

Evaluation Plan Section	Evaluation Mindset Prompt	Questions to Answer in this Section
Overview & Program Objectives	WHAT?	What program are you evaluating and when will it take place? Who is on your evaluation team? What specifically do you want participants to learn or gain from your program?
Purpose of Evaluation	WHAT?	What are you hoping to learn from the evaluation? Who will receive the evaluation data you collect (the findings) and how will the data be used for decision-making?
Timeline and Work Plan	WHAT?	What are the timeline and deadlines for your program and evaluation plan? Who is responsible for each task/deliverable?
Evaluation Questions	SO WHAT?	What questions are you asking program participants, and how are these questions directly tied to the program objectives?
Data Collection Approaches	SO WHAT?	How will you collect data from your program participants (e.g., survey, interview, existing database, etc.)?
Data Analysis Plan	SO WHAT?	How will you analyze the data you collected in a manner that is clear, meaningful, and actionable?
Dissemination Plan	NOW WHAT?	How will findings from your evaluation be shared with key individuals and used for programmatic & strategic decision-making?

Evaluation Plan Tips

Effective Evaluation Plans are...

- ✓ Written and Complete
- ✓ Saved in a location available to all key players
- ✓ Revisited frequently throughout the evaluation process
- ✓ Based on available standards & resources
- ✓ Adapted to reflect significant changes to the program and its objectives

Achievable Evaluation Plans Consider...

- ✓ Timeline
- ✓ Budget
- ✓ Your availability, your evaluation team’s capacity, and the time commitment asked from participants
- ✓ Your team members’ experience
- ✓ Strategies to overcome potential hurdles and challenges
- ✓ Frameworks, Methods, Data Collection Tools

Resources

- [CDC Evaluation Framework](#)
- [Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality \(AHRQ\): Elements of an Evaluation Plan](#)
- [University of Kansas Center for Community Health and Development Community Toolbox](#)